

Master in Sound & Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Where is the beat : introducing
'AV-PhonemeBeatSync', a multimodal
singing dataset aiming at understanding
coarticulation and rhythm in singing

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Supervisor: Lonce Wyse

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Dedication

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Thank you for those uncountable and unforgettable memories.

See you all hopefully in 5, 10, or 20 years for an SMC 2022-2023 gathering !

Until then, onto the next adventures !

As we continue ...

Abstract

Singing, the vocal production of musical tones is a key element in music. It plays a central role in the emotions perceived while listening to a musical piece, and has been present in human culture since antiquity, acting as a way to transmit information such as stories, rituals or tales from the past. Being able to sing well is considered as a valuable skill to have, and singing has shown benefits in mental and physical health. A distinctive area of Music Information Retrieval is dedicated to the analysis and synthesis of singing. Research in this domain focuses notably on understanding the singing processus, assessing performance quality, or generating automatic singing content.

While most of the approaches now uses extensive machine learning techniques, datasets are lacking, and there is none containing annotated audiovisual singing performances and none containing clear beat annotations. Previous research has been done on analyzing a singing performance and giving feedback, but none of them tried to understand where the performers line the syllables with their perception of the beat, and where the emphasis is placed.

In this Master Thesis, we present a new multimodal dataset : AV_PhonemeBeatSync, aiming at providing new annotated data to propel various research on singing analysis and synthesis. A brief analysis is conducted on the gathered data, and we find that performers, when having to sing a syllable, concentrate their attention on the vowels and disregard the consonants, regardless of their singing experience.

AV_PhonemeBeatSync contains valuable data that is worth mining, and could be used to train and evaluate neural networks aiming at visually understanding the coarticulation phenomenon, and the relationship between lyrics and rhythm.

Keywords: Singing Skill Evaluation; Coarticulation; Multimodal Dataset; Beat detection; MIRDATA; AV-PhonemeBeatSync

Chapter 1

Introduction

Singing is considered to be a desirable skill to have. It can be a hobby that brings fulfillment, and a means of connecting with others. Karaoke, jam sessions or choir allow individuals to showcase their talents and personality, and foster a sense of community. Choir participation has shown plenty of benefits (social, physical and emotional) [1].

Researchers have been wanting to understand the underlying mechanisms involved in singing : physiological & cognitive processes, vocal techniques and benefits of singing for health and memory. A part of Music Information Retrieval is dedicated to *Singing Information Processing*, a computer-assisted area of research studying singing analysis and synthesis, covering a wide range of topics like lyrics transcription, voice analysis, voice synthesis or even singing skill evaluation. They aim at understanding the physical and mental processes behind the act of singing, and using the knowledge acquired to replicate with as much richness, nuance and authenticity as possible. Lately, there has been a lot of covers of popular songs using a famous person's voice. For example, the Pokemon Theme Song as if it was sang by Linkin Park's lead singer : https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CuCUdQ3xrEk&ab_channel=Progfather

Previous research has been done on analyzing singing performances in relation to rhythm. Heydari et Al. in [2] showed promising results for a automatic beat de-

tection task in singing. However, there is still room to improvement, and relevant data seems to be lacking "*there is no existing public dataset containing clean vocal audio with beat/downbeat annotations*". This task is notoriously difficult because vocal signals are complex, featuring variations in pitch, timbre, rhythm and dynamics. Singers often introduce tempo change or expressive deviations. The outcome is dependent on the lyrics, the accents and the singing qualities of a performer. There are rarely clear and sharp onsets that can be identified. It is believed that the beat detection task could be informed with knowledge issued from phonetics and phonology [3].

Coarticulation refers to the blending (or overlapping) of articulatory movements, the superposition of multiple influences on the movement of an articulator. We can take the example of a typist. If someone could only move one finger at a time, it would be very slow. Simultaneous movements of the finger allow for rapid responding and quicker actions. There is a temporal dimension of coarticulation : the brain processes past events, present events and future events to start the actions, there is a "spillover/carryover" effect, but also a spatial dimension : the motion of one effector can affect other effectors, and once a movement is started, it cannot be instantly stopped (closed feedback loop. One movement action is the fuse of plenty of micro motions).

In the context of speech, coarticulation is a phenomenon in which the articulation of one sound influences the articulation of neighboring sounds, i.e the production of one sound begins before the completion of the previous sound, resulting in a smooth and efficient transition between sounds. In a context of singing, it plays a key role in a precise and fluid vocal performance. By anticipating the upcoming sounds, the singers ensure seamless transitions between notes and maintain a consistent sense of timing.

Timing is a fundamental aspect of singing, and rhythm consistency (singing with the appropriate tempo speed) is one of the five perceptual criterias to assess non-trained singers in a "western" approach identified by [4]. It consists of controlling the accurate placement of notes within a musical phrase.

Understanding how coarticulation influences the timing of vocal gestures would allow a singer to create seamless and connected musical phrases and improve the overall performance. It would also help the computer-based singing synthesis tasks to generate more human-like realistic content.

While the rhythmic feedback has been extensively studied in a Audio Signal Processing (ASP) based approach, there has not been a lot of interest in analyzing the importance of coarticulation in singing. However, it seems to play a crucial role in the development of a rhythm feedback approach. Singing in rhythm relies on precise timing and requires a strong coordination between the muscles involved in the process. By considering the coarticulation effects in the analysis of rhythm, we hope to gain a more comprehensive understanding of how phonemes interact and influence the rhythmic accuracy and flow of the performance.

Using the coarticulation principles to understand how singers naturally adjust their timing based on the phonetic content and context of lyrics would improve a beat detection task.

Let's analyse the word 'prove' ('P' 'R' 'UW' 'V'). If a performer had to sing this word, he would start with the lips closed ('P' is a plosive), open the lips while pronouncing the liquid 'R' before quickly moving on to the vowel 'UW' and almost closing the lips when uttering the fricative 'V'. In this example, where would someone put the emphasis ? Would it be on the mouth opening at the beginning of the plosive, or on the vowel ?

When singing, where does the performer feels the beat ? How does he lines up the phonemes with the beat, where does he puts the emphasis ? What is the influence of the phonemes in the timing of this transition ? Is it possible to predict the latency given the lyrics ? Can the latency of a performer inform on his experience ?

As said by Pan et Al. in [5], singing clearly involves more than the motion of the lower face. A complete singing face is rich in emotional and rhythmic paralingual motion of the upper face (eye and brows), head, and neck. There are, however, no available audiovisual dataset containing the face of performers. We believe that

this analysis could be done with more accuracy by using the video of performance, informing the analysis with plenty of visual cues like mouth shape, microexpressions, subtle nuances or even head movement.

In order to contribute to the development of this area of research, the AV_PhonemeBeatSync dataset is presented in this Master Thesis. It consists of audio-visual recordings of various levels of singers. We provide audios of the voice, but also the metronomic melody that the singer is listening to as well as word-level and phoneme-level annotations. We also provide high-quality high-framerate videos of the performances, that researchers could use for various audiovisual analysis tasks. While the high resolution (720p) should allow the users to manipulate them and still have details, the high framerate (60FPS) should provide insights on small details and movements happening when someone sings.

We also present a brief analysis made on the gathered data, where we give a preliminary answer to those questions, and we show that the dataset is worth mining and could be used to train neural networks for various singing-related tasks.

This document is structured as follows. First, the state-of-the-art exploring the field of phonetics, giving informed singing skill feedback in research, as well as developments in audiovisual on singing. We then describe the AV_PhonemeBeatSync dataset, how it was designed, gathered and annotated. We then explain the brief analyzes that we conducted and present some preliminary results. Finally the conclusions, future work and potentiel contributions that the AV-PhonemeBeatSync dataset could bring to the Music Information Retrieval community are described.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Perception & Cognition considerations

2.1.1 Rhythm in music

According to [6], music is perceived at multiple related timescales. It goes from notes to measures to phrases : A measure is a specific unit of time defined by a given number of beats played at a particular tempo. A phrase ¹ is defined as "*Any group of measures that has some degree of structural completeness. [...] A phrase is not pitches only, but also has a rhythmic dimension, and further, each phrase in a work contributes to that work's large rhythmic organization*". We can also define the following elements :

- rhythm : absolute timing of sound elements.
- beat : regular pulse perceived by a listener. He will tend to *feel the beat*, and synchronize his movements with it.
- meter : repeating cycle of beats. Often a pattern of variable salience, with stronger/weaker beats.

In theory, the beat is supposed to be steady or evenly spaced, but the summation of human performance and human perception of the music adds some variability,

¹[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Phrase_\(music\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Phrase_(music))

whether by an explicit choice (performance including some temporal variability), or implicit (due to the limits of temporal precision of human movements).

[7] explains that beat and meter perception can vary a lot between the listeners, influenced by passively induced elements (musical culture, appreciation, expertise, past experiences ...) or active state (paying attention or not). It is also shown that the more complex the rhythmic stimulus is, the more we can observe that the perception is different from one listener to another.

Neuroscientists found that musicians had a better ability to predict more accurately simple & complex rhythms, and that musical training (along with short-term memory capacity and beat sensitivity) played an important role in the ability to correctly perceive and reproduce rhythms. [8] [9] [10] [11][12]

2.1.2 A look into phonetics and coarticulation

Phonetics is a branch of linguistics that studies the physiological production and reception of speech (and therefore singing) sounds. Consonants implies a restriction or a closure in the vocal tract. We can classify them based on where in the vocal tract the airflow is restricted. Vowels can be classified depending on where the position of the tongue is (high, low, front, back ...). Notations are used to represent the structure and the sequence of phonemes in a word or a syllable. Some examples :

- CV : Consonant-Vowel. Example : *my*
- CVN : Consonant-Vowel-Nasal. Example : *man*
- CVVN : Consonant-Vowel-Vowel-Nasal. Here, we can see a vowel-to-vowel transition (also called diphthong). Example : *coin*
- C1VC2 : Other notation used to identify which consonant is which. Example : for *cat*, /k/ is C1, /a/ is V and /t/ is C2.

Coarticulation[13] [14] [15] has mostly been studied in phonetics where it has been noticed that speech sounds influence each other, varying with changes in the adjacent phonetic. Rousselot, early in the 19th century [16] pointed out that the lip rounding for the vowel /u/ in a VCV sequence may already start during the first vowel, noting that "*the second of two vowels is the most influential one, as can be seen in a tu in the utterance il a tourné. At the middle of the a the lips start to raise due*

to the requirements for the production of the *u*". [17], for example, showed that two vowels interact with each other across the medial consonant in a VCV scenario. According to him, producing a VCV sequence does not mean having 3 successive articulatory movements, but rather a global vowel-to-vowel movement characterized by the movement of the tongue, on which there is a superposition of the intervocalic consonant.

You, in 1979 [18] showed that the duration of friction noise (the sound produced when obstructing the airflow to cause friction) varies between 176 ms (alveolo-palatal fricatives) and 99ms (dentals). Jongman in 1989 [19] studied the duration of friction noise needed for correct identification, and showed that, after an average duration of 40ms, 50% of the total information was transmitted. During the production of diphthongs, there seems to be activation of the muscles at least 100ms before the transition from vowel to vowel occurs [20]. A similar range of timings is found for various phonetic tasks ².

Those results are dependent on plenty of factors : age, language, speed at which people are speaking, the type of transitions and phonemes... Most of those studies were done on speech, and we haven't found anything recently done involving those considerations for singing. In singing, the intelligibility is often secondary compared to the intonation and musical qualities of the voice. Vowels are sustained much longer for example.

An area of research that benefits from an extensive comprehension of those problems is be voice synthesis (vocaloids, text-to-speech, text-to-sing) for example, especially since english is a "phonetically complicated" language with a lot of coarticulation.

There have been some interest in studying the coarticulation process using machine learning, notably for speech synthesis [21]. T. Biasutto-Lervat et Al. presents in [22] an architecture used to analyze and synthesize labial coarticulation. They use an RNN-based architecture to learn a temporal relationship and detect a correlation between the data points. However, as we mentioned before, future phonemes will

²https://mitocw.ups.edu.ec/courses/linguistics-and-philosophy/24-915-linguistic-phonetics-fall-2015/lecture-notes/MIT24_915F15_lec13.pdf

Figure 1: Block diagram overview of a Bidirectional RNN

influence the production of actual and previous ones. They therefore implement a Bidirectional RNN1, that overcomes this limitation by using 2 layers simultaneously in both directions (past to future and future to past).

2.2 Singing Skill Evaluation

This area of research is part of the field of Singing Information Processing, which is a subset of Music Information Retrieval. It aims at providing feedback to singers based on their qualities and defaults, regarding professional standards of excellence. As there are a lot of musical traditions and plenty of styles of singing, we base ourselves on a mainstream western approach. The goals of computational techniques to evaluate the singing skill of a singer are to automatically measure the quality of singing just like a professional music expert would, and help the student improve, by giving him information about his singing.

2.2.1 Criteria to recognize a 'good' singer

[23] has identified a list of criterias to evaluate western classical singers based on the feedback given by expert music teachers :

- Intrinsic qualities : **Color/Warmth** (The tonal quality of the voice. Associated with a sense of depth and richness.) ; **Appropriate vibrato** (Voice correctly oscillates subtly and quickly between 2 close pitches, putting the emphasis on emotion) ; **Resonance/ring** (voice clear, sustained and vibrant that feels like ringing. It occurs when the voice is efficiently projected in the vocal cavities.) ; **Intensity** : A measure of the perceived energy. Being able to be comfortable

in soft and delicate as well as loud and powerful scenarios.

- Execution : **Flexibility** (being able to smoothly navigate between different pitches, techniques and registers) ; **Evenness of registration** (being able to successfully move through the register with a consistency in the timbre) ; **Freedom throughout vocal range** (ability to transition effortlessly through the highest, medium and lowest notes) ; **Efficient breath management** (ability to control and time-manage the air being expelled from the lungs) ; **Intonation accuracy** (ability to sing at the accurate pitch) ; **Legato line** (ability to sing with smoothly connected notes) ; **Dynamic range** (capacity to maintain the loudness across the musical piece for a variety of tones)
- **Diction** : The way that the lyrics are sung. Formulating correctly the phonemes, linking them (coarticulation), and following the rhythm correctly. Cao et Al. [4] came up with 5 perceptual evaluation criteria to assess non-trained singers in a ‘Western music type’ singing :

- Intonation accuracy : Producing and holding the correct pitch of a note in relation to the accompanying instruments or singers (*in tune*). Considered to be the most important perceptual factor when assessing singing quality [24][25]
- Rhythm consistency : appropriate tempo speed (slight variation allowed).
- Timbre brightness : brilliance of the tone, relates to the distribution of harmonics in the voice spectrum
- Vocal clarity : Vocal vibration of a clear and well-produced tone (controlled vibrato for example)
- Overall performance : Overall evaluation integrating all the perceptual parameters. A global parameter of appreciation.

Rhythm relies on precise timing and coordination between vocal articulations. By considering how phonemes interact and influence one another within a musical phrase, singers can develop a more precise sense of rhythm and improve their ability to stay in sync with the music.

2.2.2 The ‘Reference Dependent’ approach

Description of the approach

This approach is based on a simple principle : the singer will produce content that

will be compared against an ideal reference, like in [26]. This ideal reference can be MIDI notes, scores of the song or a professional rendition. These approaches are notably useful for beginners and for automatic karaoke performance assessment. This method has the advantage of being able to give feedback or grades based on the perceived musical parameters in comparison with the reference, and can work in real time. Is it, however, constrained by the need of a “golden standard” reference, therefore excluding all creativity and personal interpretation of the piece. The need for a reference also narrows the possibility in terms of track diversity (the biggest portion of the non-mainstream music will not have clear references).

This approach was popular before the advent of deep learning, and a lot of techniques are based on signal processing algorithms. Therefore, there is little machine-learning based research for this approach.

Rhythm consistency based reference dependent work

The method proposed by Tsai et Al. [27] in 2012 aims at improving the evaluation system for Karaoke performances. They implemented a mix of volume, pitch, rhythm and timbre for the scoring metric. For each song, they built an ‘in-beat model’ that they extracted from vocal signal using Hidden Markov Model (HMM) of strength vectors. They then similarly build two models : “1-beat-ahead” and “1-beat-behind” and they compare the performance of the singer for the whole song to determine a score. For their database, they obtain an accuracy or ‘in beat’/’off-beat’ of 94%. The automatic singing evaluations were close to the human ratings, with a Pearson correlation factor of 0.82.

The method presented by Molina et Al. in [28] in 2013 proposed a method for rhythmic assessment of singing performances for children and beginners (but also a pitch feedback method) using the DTW algorithm. The Dynamic Time Warping (or DTW, Fig. 2) is a algorithm used to measure the similarity between two sequences that may vary in terms of speed or timing. The algorithm aligns the elements of the sequences by warping and stretching to try to minimize the distance between key points. It is an algorithm that was really used in the rhythmic analysis. Based on the resulting shape of the DTW algorithm applied on the pitch contour of the recording and the reference, we can have some informations on the rhythmic alignment. A

Figure 2: Principle of the DTW algorithm

Figure 3: Example of the results obtained by Molina et Al. in [28]

perfectly straight line at 45° mean that the rhythmic performance is perfect (every waypoints are perfectly aligned therefore the recording is neither late nor in advance compared to the reference). Misalignment would result in deviations in this line. By computing the straightness of the line, the proposed method can give feedback on the rhythmic accuracy of the singer (compared to the reference).

The automatic singing evaluations for the rhythmic part are close to human ratings, with a Pearson correlation factor of 0.82. An example of results is found in Fig. 3

Gupta et Al. in [29] in 2017 proposes an improvement on the algorithm previously presented. They show that, because the DTW algorithm was based on the pitch contour detection, the assessment was giving a poor score of rhythm when the rhythm was good but the pitch not correct. They change the pitch contour to adopt the 13 MFCC when computing the DTW. The assumption was that, if the sequences

of phonemes and words were uttered correctly, MFCC would capture the spectral characteristics and therefore make the rhythmic measure independent of pitch inaccuracy. They show that their MFCC-based approach performs better (20% more accurate) than the previous approach. This paper also proposes a modified version of a scoring metric for singing : Perceptual Evaluation of Singing Quality (PESnQ), which takes into account parameters such as pitch, rhythm, vibrato, timbre, volume and pitch dynamic range, and shows that this new scoring metric has a correlation factor of 0.59 with the human ratings (an increase of 96% compared to PESQ).

Even if the reference dependent research is mostly ASP-based, a study done recently [30] **on drumming (and not singing)** used machine learning and obtained experts-level accurate results. They investigated an automatic performance assessment system for a student's rhythmic pattern imitation of a reference. 4 grades are possible, and the task is to automatically assign a grade to the student. Two approaches are implemented :

- A classical regression algorithm where features are the distances between the Onset Detection Functions (ODFs), the onset times and the binary onset vectors. Several regressions methods are tried (linear regression but also Gradient boosting, Random Forests ...).
- A Siamese neural network that estimates the grade of the student from an extracted onsets array for the student and the reference.

This study was done on drumming, but a similar approach for singing could obtain interesting results.

2.2.3 The 'Reference Independent' approach

Description of the approach

This approach is based on the fact that music experts can evaluate singers with a high level of consensus even when the song is new to them. This approach aims at understanding the underlying characteristics of singing quality that differentiate a 'good' performance from a 'bad' one, without the need of a reference.

With the advent of machine & deep learning, this approach has become dominant

in recent research. Instead of manually understanding what is ‘good’ and what is ‘bad’, the model can learn by itself which features to look at. This method is however limited by the quantity and quality of the datasets (and annotations). Most of the current methods only deliver a score, and not a precise feedback that could be used to help the performer improve. The longer the singing input, the better is the prediction accuracy, meaning that real-time feedback is also an ongoing challenge. It is also impossible to generalize the singing quality through every musical genre, qualities expected are not the same between a hip-hop and an opera performer. [31]

Because the model can learn by itself which features to look at, the studies are not particularly focused on giving rhythmic feedback, they are more focused on giving an overall feedback depending on plenty of parameters.

Reference Independent studies - Characterization of singing techniques

This subgroup of methods characterize the features extracted from singing renditions, and train classification or regression model with human assessment scores as a ground-truth to predict overall singing quality score.

The methodology used in [30] mentioned earlier almost fits in this category. A similar methodology not involving the comparison with a reference could be applied. The Siamese neural network would have to be modified, but the goal would remain the same : based on onset information, classify the student by giving him a grade.

Gupta et Al. in [26] proposed a framework to rank a large pool of singers according to their relative quality. Because there is no reference, they assumed that *“a song can be sung correctly by many people in a consistent way, but incorrectly in many different, dissimilar ways. The goodness of a perceptual parameter of a singer is proportional to the similarity with other singers with respect to that parameter”*. Several metrics are studied : pitch, rhythm and timbre, and several neural networks (linear regression, and 2 simple neural networks with slightly different architectures) are used to fuse all those metrics into a rank. An average is then made to create the final ranking. When comparing their ranking with human judgements, they obtained a Spearman correlation coefficient of 0.71.

Reference Independent studies - Data-driven learning approaches

This subgroup of methods is only focussed on deep learning, and does not depend on handcrafted features. The success of those methods relies on the design of the network architecture, but also on the quality and quantity of the data.

Zhang et Al. in [32] proposed a CNN architecture named Bi-DenseNet that used the magnitude spectrogram as input representation and was trained in a supervised way to discriminate good singing rendition from bad ones. From a social media, they gathered nearly 20.000 pure solo singing clips and humanly classified them as ‘good’ or ‘bad’ (a 3 to 5s short sequence is sufficient for judging good/poor). To feed the neural network, they used the spectrogram of the recordings. With this method, they obtained 89.55% accuracy. However, this approach is purely binary, and does not provide any more information to the performer.

Huang et Al. in [33] designed a convolutional recurrent neural network (CRNN) to learn features from the input and predict evaluation scores. They make a comparison between several types of 2D spectral features representation as the CRNN input :

- Mel-spectrogram : a spectrogram represented in the mel-scale to be consistent with the known human perception.
- Constant-Q Transform (CQT) : a time-frequency representation with logarithmically scaled frequencies.
- Chromagram : a representation of the energy distribution over a set of pitch classes

They used a CRNN with a 3-Layer CNN (to learn more high-level representations and capture more intricate patterns) followed by a RNN layer with GRUs (to capture long-range dependencies) followed by a fully-connected dense layer that will allow the network to extract non-linear mapping from the features, enabling regression. For an hybrid CRNN approach (cf Fig. 4, they used a pitch histogram as a conditioning vector after the recurrent layer, as they realized that a good singer’s histogram would have narrow and sharp peaks while a bad singer’s histogram would be more dispersed.

As the ground truth, they ranked 100 singers using a crowdsourcing platform and

Figure 4: Hybrid-CRNN architecture used by Huang et Al. in [33]

obtained a Best-Worst Scaling (BWS) score. When comparing their results with human rating, they obtained a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.76 with the hybrid CRNN for the CQT representation. Having a score is still better than a binary result, but there is still not clear feedback given to the performer.

Gupta et Al. in [34] focus their study on rhythm, and mention that without the ground truth, the task is complex. However, they come up with a new idea : the syllable duration histogram to inform the neural network. They used a dataset with professional singers that has time annotations for phonemes and syllables that they augmented by creating some time-shifted data. Using the scores, they show that there is less than 100ms of difference between the note and the syllable for 81% of the tokens. They used the previously presented Hybrid CRNN architecture, with the 2D CQT representation as the input, and the syllable-histogram as a conditioning vector. When comparing their results with human rating, they obtain a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.75 with the hybrid CRNN for the CQT representation.

2.3 Multimodal-based approaches related to singing

While there are already plenty of multimodal-based studies that have been conducted on speech (several datasets, several languages . . .), there has not been a lot of studies yet regarding singing. As said in [35], *“A singer sacrifices some richness of linguistic features such as word stress and articulation to compensate for musical features such as melody or tempo. Singing is generally less intelligible than speech.”*

The methods that are applied to speech must be adapted to fit a singing envi-

Figure 5: Example of the content found in SingingFace - [35]

Figure 6: Example of the 96x96 pixels content found in MM-ALT - [40]

ronment. Recent advances in audio-visual speech recognition ([36],[37]) show that audio-visual models perform better than their audio-only counterparts. This suggests that including additional sensory information on top of the acoustic signal would enhance the performance of an automatic lyric transcription system.

2.3.1 An overview of the singing audio-visual datasets

Machine learning tasks require quantitative and qualitative datasets for the training processes. However, until very recently, there was almost no audio-visual dataset for a singing task in science. On March 2023, Liu et Al. introduced SingingFace [35]. They collected 600 Chinese and English singing videos for a total of 40 hours, recorded at 30FPS. However, when giving access to the dataset, they don't provide the singing videos, but the reconstructed 3DMM model coefficients (cf Fig. 5), which are supposed to help us reconstruct the extracted facial information. Moreover, they did not aligned manually the videos and the audios, but they used SyncNet [38], a model aiming at synchronizing the mouth motion and the speech. As we know, speech and singing are very different processes. Because singing is usually constrained by a sense of rhythm, the utterance might not be perfect, and the words are sometimes unintelligible. We can therefore assume that the audiovisual synchronization might not be perfect. They also don't provide the ground truth for singing and accompaniment, but used Spleeter [39], a source separation model.

In 2022, Gu et Al. [40] presented the first (as we know of) multimodal dataset of singing including the face of the singer. They gathered 30 participants with various exposure to singing, and various accents. A total of more than 5 hours of content was gathered. They recorded the voice of the singers, their face and the kinesthetic activity of the head, jaw and lips during the process. They gave the singers freedom of pitch and rhythm, while they were listening to an accompanying melody. The video is at 25 frames per second, they used the Dlib library [41] to cut out 96x96 Regions-Of-Interests (ROIs) centered around the mouth (cf Fig. 6). They cut the recordings into plenty of small extracts, and annotated the duration and the lyrics uttered without giving precise timings. When recording, they asked the participants to minimize their body movements such as facial gestures or body swaying. They also cropped out the videos without giving the coordinates of the extracted facial landmarks. Moreover, some of the accompaniment doesn't have a clear rhythmic pattern, so it is therefore hard to use this data for a rhythm-based analysis.

There are also other datasets like Acapella [42] that consist of solo singing videos sourced from YouTube, sampled across different singers and languages. All the extracts share common characteristics : Single frontal face view of the singer without occlusions, minimal background noise, no beatboxing or snapping fingers, all the songs have lyrical content (no humming or yodeling for example). There are, however, almost no annotations for this data, except the language of the singer and the sex.

2.3.2 A quick overview of audiovisual researches on singing

Lip-reading in singing

The MM-ALT study presented earlier made by Gu et Al. in [40] is a very interesting paper for a multimodal approach of singing analysis. The paper aims at presenting a system for Automatic lyric transcription, proposing several methods for subtopics such as Lip reading in singing, or an Inertial Measurement Unit-based voice activity detection.

They designed a multi-encoder based architecture, presented in Fig. 7, composed of

Figure 7: Architecture presented in MM-ALT - [40]

a feature representation learning frontend (cf below) and an automatic lyric transcription backend that aims at transforming the resulting features into sentences.:

- Video encoder is derived from the AV-HuBERT architecture [43] which is the state of art for lip reading for speech tasks.
- Audio encoder derived from wav2vec2.0 [44], with fine-tuning on singing datasets
- IMU encoder is a CRNN with 1D convolutional layers and GRUs.
- Feature Fusion block. Here, they introduce Residual Cross Attention (RCA) to fuse the multimodal features using self-attention and cross-attention mechanisms.

For this very first attempt, they obtained 47.91% word error rate on the validation split and 68.45% word error rate on the test split, showing promising results.

Synchronizing audio and video

Audio-video synchronization refers to the process of aligning a vocal performance with the corresponding video footage. The audiovisual synchronization for speech has already been tackled with great success (SyncNet [38] showed nearly 94.1% accuracy). Compared to speech, singing poses challenges because of the different ways of phrasing, sustained vowels and sometimes complex rhythmic patterns.

In work presented by [45], the authors try to determine if lips motion and voice in a video are synchronized or not, using a novel AudioVisual transformer-based model introduced in the paper. They improve the state of the art for speech synchronization on the LRS2 standard dataset, but they are also the first ones to propose results for a multimodal analysis of singing, using the Acappella dataset. They obtain up to 99.8% accuracy for a 0.6s speech video clip, and up to 85.2% accuracy for a 1s singing clip.

Audiovisual singing synthesis

With the growing interest in digital avatars and 3D facial animation (for animated movies, but also for everything related to the metaverse ...). The challenge is to realistically synthesize an animated singing face based on an audio recording. There are companies like JaLi³ that are focusing on this research, and interesting results have been obtained by Pan et Al. in [5] in a singing-comprehension based approach, but also in a more computer-science and deep-learning based approach in [35]

2.4 Two tasks related to rhythm in singing : lyrics alignment and beat detection

2.4.1 Lyrics alignment

Lyrics-to-audio alignment focuses on synchronizing the lyrics (words/phonemes) of a song with its corresponding audio recording. This enables technologies such as karaoke content generation, speech recognition for singing and automatic transcription of vocal performances.

K. Schulze-Forster in [46] presents a joint approach to phoneme level lyrics alignment and singing voice separation based on a newly introduced DTW-attention algorithm (attention-based Dynamic Time Warping algorithm), and matches the observed phoneme sequences (inputted data) to the observed audio frames. For the phonemes alignment, he reaches a Percentage of Correctly Aligned Segments (PCAS) 85.94% for noiseless monophonic singing.

J. Huang et Al. in [47] is the current state of the art for lyrics alignment. He presents a multi-task method, where the lyrics alignment is the primary goal and the pitch detection is a secondary goal. This idea is inspired by the works of [48][49] that showed that multi-task learning can lead to improved accuracy, and that pitch could be a good candidate. This method achieves up to 95% accuracy for the Percentage of Correct Onsets (PCO) (0.3 seconds of tolerance).

³<https://jaliresearch.com/>

Figure 8: Architecture used in SingNet - [2]

Performance from the current lyrics transcription systems remains far from perfect. Some genres are more complicated than others, and they are also heavily dependent on the language.

2.4.2 Beat detection

Heydari et Al. in [2] in 2023 presents SingNet, the first system that aims at tracking beats and downbeats of singing voices in real-time. For each audio frame, a CRNN-based model detects if there's a beat, a downbeat or a non-beat. They also introduce a particle filtering model that incorporates the inferences resulting from all the historical data. Particle filtering is a probabilistic estimation technique used to track and estimate the state of a system that evolves over time. It is applied in scenarios where the system's behavior is uncertain. They obtain the following results :

- For a tolerance of $\pm 70\text{ms}$:
 - 59.53% accuracy on the beat for their data
 - 38.04% accuracy on the downbeat for their data
- For a tolerance of $\pm 200\text{ms}$ as the human tolerance to beat and downbeat error can be larger:
 - 75.65% accuracy on the beat for their data
 - 49.24% accuracy on the downbeat for their data

They also compared with the GTZAN dataset, after extracting the vocal stems (the data being therefore more noisy and harder to understand). An issue is however raised, as the author mentions that *“there is no existing public dataset containing clean vocal audio with beat/downbeat annotations”*.

Chapter 3

AV_PhonemeBeatSync

As we previously noted, there are gaps in the multimodal research on the singing analysis and synthesis tasks. To contribute to this effort, we are gathering a dataset that will bring new data and could be used by researchers for various singing-related tasks.

This section outlines the processes behind the creation of the AV_PhonemeBeatSync dataset. We will answer those questions : What is an interesting ground truth for our tasks ? How to collect data in a qualitative way ? How to process the data, and what annotations could be useful ? How to address the privacy concerns ?

3.1 Content

To design the content of the dataset, some questions guided our process, and we mention them here. The dataset is providing researchers with multimodal data :

- Audios of several participants singing the same melodies : their voice and the melody that they listen to while performing, in order to have the rhythmic ground truth.
- Videos showing the face of the participant while he performs.

However, there is still plenty of freedom regarding the content, and we took some decisions to guide the content creation :

3.1.1 Regarding the base melodies :

Because we want to know how people put phonemes on the beat, how they put the emphasis, the background must remain simple, and the performer be comfortable with the rhythmic background no matter his singing experience. We must set up a situation where almost everybody would intuitively know the rhythm, and therefore when they know where the beat is supposed to happen.

we opt for widely recognized, single-instrument melodies that are easy to follow. Children's lullabies, being both well-known and in the public domain, fit this criterion perfectly.

We select 5 children lullabies with simple melody that lasts between 30 and 40 seconds, and that people know entirely, not just one line or one short part.

- Twinkle Twinkle Little Star : The most known one, instantly recognizable. It is used twice, as it is the perfect way to introduce the process with a simple version, and used later in the experiment to make a harder version.
- Old McDonald had a farm
- Frère Jacques
- Ode to joy
- Mary had a little lamb

All the melodies are reproduced in Ableton. In order for them to be 100 BPM steady, small modifications are made to remove syncopation in some tracks.

3.1.2 Regarding the lyrics :

What we want : At a macro level, we are interested in analyzing the coarticulation process when singing in the English language. To be as broad as possible, we want our corpora to give a representation phonetic overview in the English language. We therefore want to have a wide variety of phonetic transitions, but also a corpus that's a phoneme distribution of the lyrics that follows the phoneme distribution of the English language. The lyrics must be laid out in a way that feels natural to the performer while providing interesting transitions.

Lyrics generation

Choice was made to generate baseline lyrics using ChatGPT and then to refine the results. The final versions are presented in the Appendix. We present an example of a ChatGPT output in Fig.9 and the reworked version in Fig.10

Verse 2:

The food in Barcelona's divine
 From tapas to paella, it's all fine
 Savor seafood fresh from the sea
 Or churros dipped in chocolate, yes please
 The wine flows freely all night long
 As we revel in Barcelona's song
 Of passion, flavor, and romance
 Barcelona, you have me entranced

Figure 9: Example of verse generated by ChatGPT

Bar	ce	lo	na	ci	ty	gran-	-d
Beach	moun	tai-	-n	sea	and	san-	-d
Go	thic's	quar	ter	co	bbled	lane	Ram
bla	with	out	a	rai-	-n		
Of	mu	sic	laugh	ter	de	li-	-ght
Ca	ta	la-	-n	shi	ning	bri-	-ight
With	cul	ture	art	his	to-	-ry	it's
all	l	want	to	see-	-ee		

Figure 10: Same verse after rework

We can identify some issues in the ChatGPT output presented Fig. 9:

- Some lines are way too long and don't fit in the 8-beat pattern ("Or churros dipped in chocolate, yes please" would take +/- 10 beats depending on how we line up).
- Some lines could fit the 8-beat pattern but it would feel too rushed and probably too hard to utter ("From tapas to paella, it's all fine").
- There is no room for breathing.
- Too much repetitions (Barcelona is there 3 times)
- Some repetition of phonetic transitions (divine/fine, long/song ...)

We therefore modify lyrics in order to make them fit, lay them out in a way that feels natural to the performer, being not too hard to read and give a variety of phonetic transitions (CVC, VCV, CVVC for various phonemes ...).

Regarding the phonetic distribution : To compare the phoneme distribution of our lyrics with the phoneme distribution of every word in the English language we use the CMU Pronouncing Dictionary¹, an pronunciation dictionary for North American English that contains over 130.000 words and their respective pronunciations. While the words contained in the CMU dictionary account for nearly 850.000, one

¹<http://www.speech.cs.cmu.edu/cgi-bin/cmudict>

of our performers will utter 4000 phonemes. Our aim is to prove that those distributions are statistically correlated i.e. that we respect the distribution within the English language.

Figure 11: Comparing the two phonemes distributions

Figure 12: Comparing the proportions for each phoneme between the 2 distributions and with the Pearson linear correlation coefficient

Fig 11 illustrates the comparable phoneme proportions across both distributions, displaying a consistent trend. The Pearson correlation factor, calculated to confirm correlation, yields **0.94** with an incredibly low p-value of **1.85e-19**. This strong correlation is further substantiated by the histogram of distribution differences, which conforms to a normal distribution. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is also employed, assessing the likelihood of sample similarity to a given probability distribution. Our analysis, utilizing a fitting algorithm, reveals that

$$X \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma^2) \quad \text{with } \mu = 0 \text{ and } \sigma^2 = 0.706$$

Applying the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test on our data results in a value of **0.23** with a p-value of **0.25**, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis.

We therefore proved that the 2 distributions are correlated.

3.1.3 Linking lyrics with melodies :

To explore a singer's beat perception, we emphasize the rhythmic dimension. Using a steady 100 BPM metronomic pattern in the melodic track, we provide singers with rhythmic guidance for synchronized lyric delivery. This tempo accommodates comfortable reading, singing pace, and breathing. Performers are prompted to align with most beats, whether through various phonemes or pauses for breath.

3.1.4 Decision regarding the performers:

Each performer records 16 minutes of singing in total, divided in several melodies. Those choices are motivated by several factors :

- Some performers are not be experienced, so asking them for too much content would deteriorate their performance.
- Having several melodies allows the recording process to not be too boring and keeps the performer motivated and involved in the process. It also brings some diversity in the utterance of phonemes, and allows for different levels of complexity. Some performers might also be more familiar with some songs than others, so it might reduce the disparity between performers.
- A protocol (described later) puts every performers on the same level with rehearsals and guided discovery of the lyrical content.

3.2 Recording : How to gather the content

For an audiovisual dataset like AV-PhonemeBeatSync, the recording process is a key element. We need to gather qualitative data, in a controlled manner : the performers must give us what we want and how we want it. There must be some form of homogeneity in the data.

A way to proceed could have been to ask the performers to record themselves in their environment, alone. This would have helped to gather more participants, and increase the diversity in the dataset (various ages and mother tongues), but the resulting data would've been less qualitative (less controlled process and guidance).

The main issue with this way of recording is that it would have been harder to have the rhythmic ground truth: at what moment does the person feel the beat.

Having this rhythmic information is the main goal of our dataset, and this information needs to be as precise as possible. Therefore, we decide to record the performers in a controlled environment, ensuring the quality of the content.

3.2.1 Technical choices :

While audio recordings boast near-null granularity due to a 48kHz sample rate (equating to a value every 0.02ms), video operates on a larger scale. Many audio-visual datasets capture at 25 or 30 FPS (a frame every 40 or 33 ms). To ensure informative quality, we've opted for 60 FPS, providing granularity at a frame every 16.7ms.

As mentioned in the state of the art, speech articulation spans nearly 100ms. In singing, emphasis rests more on vowels and less on consonants. The advantage of finer data granularity becomes apparent, offering insights into facial intricacies during phonetic shifts and transitions that can be crucial during singing.

Regarding the resolution, we choose the 720p format (1280x720). It offers a balance between file size, computational requirements and great visual details. We have a clear visual representation of the performers' facial expressions and mouth movements. Having this high resolution data can allow researchers to use processing algorithms on it later and still have some precisions.

Method used for the rhythmic groundtruth : We want to provide to the researchers a dataset containing clean vocal audio with beat/downbeat annotations [2]. In order to achieve the highest precision, we follow this strategy :

- We reproduce the melody and add a metronomic pattern. We are playing this background in the performer's ears while recording him singing on Ableton.
- The melodic background leaves some time at the beginning and the end for the performer to realize synchronization tasks as described in 3.2.2.
- All latency will then be removed during the editing phase : we know what the performer was listening to while he sings.

Material used : To do the recording, we use the following elements :

Figure 13: Descriptive picture of the setup

- A camera : GoPro Hero6². Reliable, and films at 720p - 59.94FPS.
- A microphone : Shure VP88³.
- A sound card : To interface the microphone with the laptop, we use the Scarlett Solo by Focusrite⁴.
- A recording software : We record the voice using Ableton Live 11⁵
- Headphones : Sennheiser HD25⁶. Professional studio monitoring equipment.

Closed headset to reduce potential leaks of the melody into the microphone.

Apparatus in picture : A picture of our setup is presented in Fig. 13.

3.2.2 Recording protocol

In order to have the most homogeneous and qualitative recordings, we follow a protocol for every recording session :

- The performer is informed of the goal of the study and signs the consent form stating that he allows me to record, manipulate and publish his performance.
- Collect some personal information that will be included in the dataset :
 - Age & Sex
 - Mother tongue : Even if the lyrics are in English, singing is an intimate process where emotions can arise and influence the way someone utters

²<https://gopro.com/es/es/update/hero6>

³<https://pubs.shure.com/guide/VP88/en-US>

⁴<https://focusrite.com/products/scarlett-solo>

⁵<https://www.ableton.com/en/live/>

⁶<https://fr-fr.sennheiser.com/casque-dj-on-ear-hd25>

- words when singing. Having a wide variety of accents, of pronunciations, of singing styles should help to have more accent-resistant models.
- Experience singing. 4 categories are presented to the participant, and he has to choose the most accurate one :
 - * Complete beginner : Someone that almost never sings.
 - * Casual singer : Someone that sings sometime, for pleasure. Under the shower, for a karaoke, with some friends . . .
 - * Experimented singer : Someone that sings/sang in a group, choir or that took lessons. Confident about his singing skills.
 - * Professional singer : Someone that sings professionally or has a lot of experience. Feels very comfortable with the singing process.
 - Generic instructions are given to the performers :
 - They have to sing as naturally as possible, just like they would do under the shower or to a young family member.
 - They have complete freedom on the pitch, but must try to be as accurate as possible on the timing (while still remaining natural).
 - They have to keep the focus and singing as long as they are not stopped. If there are too many mistakes or a mistake too big, the current song must be restarted from the beginning.
 - They must behave naturally, and can move their head or body parts as long as it doesn't interfere with the recording. Slightly moving the head, waving the hand, tapping the rhythm along the leg . . .
 - They must try to face the camera, but a small degree is allowed.
 - At any moment, if the performers feels uncomfortable or are too tired, he can leave the room and stop / postpone the recording session.
 - The recording process is described to them (cf point below and Fig. 14.
 - Once the instructions are given, the recordings can start. There are 12 parts of 1mn20 to record for each participant. For every part, the process is the following :
 - Listening once to the melody.
 - For every part, the lyrics are read and sung together, and indications for difficulties are given. The lyrics are presented to the performer on a screen.

- Rehearsing. As much as needed. As long as the performer does not feel comfortable and ready to sing, the recording does not start.
- When the performer feels ready, the recording can start.

Figure 14: Recording process represented as a diagram

In order to simplify the recording process, templates for every song were created, and the layout of every Ableton project is the same and is presented in Fig 15:

Figure 15: Layout of every Ableton project

- **Preparation phase** where the performer has to clap face camera and put the headset on the microphone. This phase lasts 4 bars.
- **Blank phase** : A 1-bar phase without noise : At this time, the performer should put the headset back on his head
- **Metronomic phase** : A 1-bar phase with the metronome only. For the performer to prepare himself and adapt himself to the rhythm.
- **Performance phase** : At this time, the melody starts and the performer can sing
- **End phase** : the person claps again face camera and puts the headset close to the microphone again.

Recording is an intense process as singing is very intimate, and most of the performers are not used to singing in public, while being recorded. One of my tasks, during those recording sessions, is to make the performer comfortable, by providing a ‘safe place’, a positive environment without judgment.

3.3 Processing the data

Once the recording phase is complete, we possess the raw data. Our next tasks are: meticulous editing to ensure seamless synchronization among all elements and preparing the annotations. This section is dedicated to explain the steps undertaken in crafting the AV_PhonemeBeatSync dataset.

3.3.1 Editing

The editing is done on DaVinci Resolve ⁷. The goal of this process is to synchronize 3 elements for every parts performed by every performer. We end with :

- 312 Video files without sound. Between 80 and 100s. (720p, mp4 - H.264 codec, 59.94 FPS)
- 312 Audio files corresponding to the voice. Between 80 and 100s. (48kHz, wav with 16 bit depth)
- 312 Audio files corresponding to the background melody heard by the performer. Between 80 and 100s. (48kHz, wav with 16 bit depth)

For every part of the recording, a timeline is created. Within this timeline, we put the 3 corresponding elements to synchronize. Then, we follow this process:

- We amplify the audio corresponding to the voice (around +10dB but it depends on the recording, some people sing louder than others).
- Audio/Video synchronization : We look for the starting clap, and align the clap recorded by the GoPro and by the microphone together. This gives us a +/- 1 frame accuracy.
- Audio/Audio synchronization : We look for the beat in the audio recorded by the microphone, and sync exactly with the corresponding beat in the background melody. This gives us less than 1ms accuracy.

⁷<https://www.blackmagicdesign.com/products/davinciresolve>

- We verify that the ending clap and the ending beats are still synchronized.
- We cut the beginning of the recording exactly 1 bar before the melody starts (therefore 1 bar before the performer starts), and cut the end of the recording before the participant does the finishing clap.

3.3.2 Privacy concern

A question that rose quickly when designing the dataset has been the privacy question. From the few examples that we have (for singing but mostly for speaking), audiovisual datasets can be divided into 2 categories :

- “In the wild” datasets : They consist of content found online. They are usually massive, with plenty of different sources and content. However, they are usually not carefully curated with precise & refined annotations. They lean toward quantity more than quality. They are particularly useful for deep learning, where the model will learn by itself what needs to be learned. As the content can be found freely on the internet, those are not anonymous, and contain full faces.

Acapella [42] is an example of ‘In the wild’ dataset.

- “Curated” datasets : They consist of new content created specifically for a task. As they require participants, they have less content, but they are carefully curated, annotated and designed. They lean toward quality more than quantity. They also can be used for machine learning and deep learning, and it’s possible to use data augmentation techniques by applying small modifications to the data (for image/video : randomly cropping, flipping, changing the angle ; for audio : adding noise, filtering, cutting). However, as it requires participants donating their personal data, they are most of the time anonymous.

MM-Alt[40] and Singing faces[35] are the only existing audiovisual datasets of people singing, and they both have anonymous data. An example of a speech multimodal dataset openly displaying the faces is Speaking Faces ⁸.

Our dataset, AV-PhonemeBeatSync falls in the second category, and it would make sense to anonymize the performers. However, we want to provide researchers with

⁸<https://issai.nu.edu.kz/speaking-faces/>

the full faces of the singers, in order to capture all the little details that a singer can have. As said in [5] : “Singing clearly involves more than the motion of the lower face. A complete singing face is rich in emotional and rhythmic paralingual motion of the upper face (eye and brows), head, and neck. [...] an exciting avenue for future work is the prediction of eyebrows, gaze, blink, and head and neck movements to emotionally and rhythmically accompany the lower face in song.”

A choice is therefore made : restricting the access to the video files. In order to access them, the access will have to be requested to the creators and a NDA agreement will have to be signed.

However, in order for everyone to use the dataset for an audio-visual machine learning task, we are going to extract the facial data points of the performance and have them in free access.

For this, we are using two facial extraction algorithms : Dlib & Mediapipe.

Dlib [41] <http://dlib.net/> : “Dlib is a general purpose cross-platform open source software library written in C++. Its design is heavily influenced by ideas from design by contract and component-based software engineering. This means it is, first and foremost, a collection of independent software components.”

We are going to use the *face_landmark_detection* algorithm ⁹ that aims at finding frontal human faces in an image and estimate their pose. The pose takes the form of 68 landmarks, that are shown in Fig. 16.

The deep learning model used is a reproduction of the algorithm described in [50]. The Dlib library can also be used to align each frame to a reference face frame via affine transformation, and to crop a region-of-interest (ROI) centered on the mouth, like in the N20EM dataset [40], or in this work : [43].

Mediapipe [51] : Mediapipe is a face extraction algorithm that has been designed to detect and extract human faces from images and video streams. The model is fast enough to be considered real-time, with a javascript version that can be used to embark the model in a web browser-based application. The model extracts 468 facial coordinates (Fig. 17), providing more depth and information than Dlib. This landmark extraction algorithm was used, for example, to develop a Lip Reading

⁹http://dlib.net/face_landmark_detection.py.html

Figure 16: 68 landmarks extracted by Dlib

Figure 17: 468 landmarks extracted by Mediapipe

model for Turkish [52].

For the facial extraction : For every video, we extract for every frame the facial landmarks of the performer, and store the data in a file.

Because the landmarks are extracted according to a pattern, it is possible to filter points of interest and focus on some parts of the face if the application requires it. The landmarks are values between 0 and 1. Multiplying by the desired height and width will give the facial reconstruction. Any dimension works, but it is intended for 16/9.

3.3.3 Annotations

In order to have a dataset that is easily usable and accessible, we are going to publish the dataset to MIRDATA ¹⁰. MIRDATA is an open-source python library that standardizes how some MIR datasets are accessed and used, providing tools to download the dataset, validating the presence and the integrity of the files, loading annotations and metadata.

In order to publish the Dataset to MIRDATA, we have to follow their guidelines, that include a standard hierarchy to follow.

All the files share the same format :

SW_X.Y.Z

Singer $W \in [01, 26]$, Melody $X \in [1, 6]$, Part $Y \in [1, 2]$, Format $Z \in \{\text{json, txt, wav, mp4}\}$

¹⁰<https://mirdata.readthedocs.io/en/latest/source/overview.html>

```

> Example_Dataset/
  > audio/
    track1.wav
    track2.wav
    track3.wav
  > annotations/
    track1.csv
    track2.csv
    track3.csv
  > metadata/
    metadata_file.csv

```

Figure 18: Dataset hierarchy proposed by MIRDATA

```

> AV-PhonemeBeatSync/
  > video/
    S1_1.1.mp4 => Singer 1, song 1.1
    ...
  > voice/
    S1_1.1.wav => Singer 1, song 1.1
    ...
  > melody/
    S1_1.1.wav => Singer 1, song 1.1
    ...
  > facelandmarks_dlib/
    S1_1.1.txt => Singer 1, song 1.1
    ...
  > facelandmarks_mediapipe/
    S1_1.1.txt => Singer 1, song 1.1
    ...
  > annotation/
    S1_1.1.json => Singer 1, song 1.1
    ...

```

Figure 19: AV_PhonemeBeatSync hierarchy

```

▼ object {6}
  ▼ singer {4}
    age : 26
    sex : M
    mother_tongue : French
    experience : Casual
  ► beat_at [53]
  ► text [53]
  ► phonemes [53]
  ► phonemes_timings [53]
  ► uttered_properly [53]

```

Figure 20: Structure of the annotation file

- singer : corresponds to the personal information provided by the performer.
- beat_at : array corresponding to the beat location ground truth (when did the singer heard the beat). We use the ‘High Frequency Content’¹¹ algorithm to detect the onsets. This algorithm is the best here as we are trying to detect a percussive event.
- text : array corresponding to the lyrics that the performer had to sing. Each element is the portion of text that was shown to the performer. This is considered the ground truth for the lyrics.
- phonemes : array containing the ground truth for the various phonemes that correspond to the text that is being sung. The phonemes were extracted using the CMU dictionary. Some precisions however :
 - The CMU dictionary is based on speech. However, when singing, the way to pronounce words changes : sustaining the syllables, adding variation, putting the emphasis on some phonemes . . . For our case, some phonemes translations given by the CMU dictionary didn’t fit with the way that people had to pronounce them, so we had to adapt some elements.
 - Some words can have several pronunciations. Depending on the melodic and lyrical context, different utterances could be made for the same word.
 - Some people have stronger accents than others and therefore utter the

¹¹https://essentia.upf.edu/tutorial_rhythm_onsetdetection.html

word differently.

Therefore, this ground truth corresponds to “what the performer should sing, but not how he sung it. This data might be biased or might not fit with the reality of the recording

- `phonemes_timings` : array corresponding to the timing where the phonemes are uttered. cf below for a detailed explanation.
- `uttered_properly` : array corresponding to the correct or the wrong utterance of the text. It can be just a wrong word (‘who’ instead of ‘where’), reading the word wrong (‘good’ vs ‘god’), or loosing the rhythm and delaying several portions of text. A listening was done of every recording, and every time an error was detected, if it was noted down. The resulting array is composed of ‘True’ (it was uttered correctly) or ‘False’ (it was uttered incorrectly).

Phoneme timings : To obtain the phonemes timing onsets, we use the model introduced by K.Schulze-Forster in [46]. Here, the scenario is ideal. We have a voice without any noise or background, and there is no need for source separation. In this scenario, the phonemes are aligned with a median Absolute Error (absolute difference between the true and the estimated onset) of nearly 16ms, which approximately corresponds to 1 video frame. The mean Absolute Error is nearly 80ms however. This tells us that whenever there is an error, it can be pretty wide.

While it would be too time consuming to verify everything precisely, we take some random extracts and manually annotate them using Praat¹², to compare, on a small sample. We found that, for our context, the model extracted the timings with a surprising precision. On our small scale tests, without the big errors we’ve add a mean error of 13.21ms, which is less than a video frame.

However, some errors were spotted. In the example presented in Fig. 21, we can see that the ‘F’ consonant is mistook with a breathing from the performer. Thankfully, a mistake for one phoneme does not influence all of the remainder of the timing extraction, but a local part.

¹²<https://www.fon.hum.uva.nl/praat/>

Figure 21: Example of an error from the model

Figure 22: Repartition of the various categories of performers

Figure 23: Repartition of the various mother tongues

3.4 AV_PhonemeBeatSync : A summary

- 26 performers : 14 (54%) identified themselves as males and 12 (46%) identified themselves as females.
- Performers aged 20 to 62 with an average age of 27 years old and a majority having between 21 and 24 years old.
- A variety of mother tongues : 7 of them are represented, with a majority of Spanish performers
- Most of the performers (14 - 54%) considered themselves casuals while the remaining considered themselves beginners (4 - 15%), experienced (6 - 23%) or professionals (2 - 8%).
- Each performer sang nearly 16mn30, a total of 7 hours of content.
- More than one million five hundred thousand frames.

Chapter 4

Evaluation

In this section, we are going to present the methodology behind some simple analysis of the annotated data that we collected. We are going to give some elements to answer the following questions :

- Is it possible to classify a performer by skill using only the rhythmic information in our dataset ?
- When do people line up phonemes with the beat in our dataset ?
- Where do people line up phonemes with the beat in our dataset ?

4.1 Methodology

4.1.1 Classification of a performer

We want to classify a performer using the rhythmic information in our dataset.

We do this 2 subsets of the dataset : the complete AV-PhonemeBeatSync (unbalanced for our task) and a balanced extract of AV-PhonemeBeatSync, with the informations of 2 performers of each category. Cf Table 1.

To realize this task, we are going to use two methods :

- Classification using several machine learning algorithms. We compute the Confusion Matrix for the most efficient model.
- A Simple Neural network.

	Beginner	Casual	Experimented	Professional
Unbalanced data (items - %age)	48 - 15.38%	168 - 53.84%	72 - 23.07%	24 - 7.7%
Balanced data (items - %age)	24 - 25%	24 - 25%	24 - 25%	24 - 25%

Table 1: Repartition of elements in the 2 datasets

```

Beat detected at 3.633922815322876
Associated text : gli
Associated phonemes : ['G', 'L', 'IH']
Associated phonemes timings : [3.472, 3.536, 3.584]
Is the text uttered properly ? True
--> The delay computed is : (3.47 - 3.63)*1000 = -161.92ms

Beat detected at 4.22603178024292
Associated text : mmer
Associated phonemes : ['M', 'ER']
Associated phonemes timings : [4.096, 4.16]
Is the text uttered properly ? True
--> The delay computed is : (4.1 - 4.23)*1000 = -130.03ms

Beat detected at 4.8297505378723145
Associated text : li
Associated phonemes : ['L', 'IH']
Associated phonemes timings : [4.576, 4.8]
Is the text uttered properly ? True
--> The delay computed is : (4.58 - 4.83)*1000 = -253.75ms

Beat detected at 5.433469295501709
Associated text : ttle
Associated phonemes : ['T', 'AH', 'L']
Associated phonemes timings : [5.232, 5.392, 5.408]
Is the text uttered properly ? True
--> The delay computed is : (5.23 - 5.43)*1000 = -201.47ms

```

Figure 24: Example of delay computed

Data preparation

We have given a task to our performers : to sing some lyrics on the beat as naturally as they can while they respect the rhythm. Because we have the ground truth of the rhythm (we know what lyrics they are supposed to sing and when they actually utter the phonemes), we can actually verify if they are on time or not, and compute the delay for each transition.

For each recording, we are going to calculate the delay for each transition. This information will then be turned into a histogram, with 72 bins that range from -600ms to 600ms. This gives us a granularity of 16.67ms, just like the framerate of our videos.

An example of how the delay is computed can be found in fig 24, while the histogram for one performance can be found in fig 25.

Figure 25: Histogram of a single performance

Figure 26: Architecture of our fully connected neural network

LazyPredict : is a Python library that helps build a lot of basic models without much code and helps understand which models work better without any hyperparameter tuning. We use LazyPredict on the datasets, and see which models work the best for our cases.

While we don't expect to be able to perfectly identify the experience of a singer just by his rhythmic information for this dataset, we are hoping to find some interesting results that could motivate a deeper analysis. Some previous results presented in the state of the art showed that the assessment of singing performances for children and beginners was informed by rhythmic information [28][29][34]

Simple Neural Network

We also design a dense fully connected neural network. After experimenting with the architecture and the hyperparameters, we end up with the architecture presented in Fig. 26

- Input Layer : 72 bins of the input histogram
- 4 Hidden Layers : Fully connected dense layers. We have a mix of tanH and reLu. We also have 0.40 Dropout per layer in order to delay the overfitting.
- Output Layer : 4 classes, we have a Softmax activation.

4.1.2 When do performers line up lyrics with the beats

Similarly as in 4.1.1, we can compute the delay for each transition. However, here, we are going to divide the transitions into a variety of phonetic transitions, and we'll

Categories	Explained	Example - text	Example - phonemes
V V	Last phoneme previous block : vowel Phoneme that follows : vowel.	'the air'	'DH', 'AH' 'EH', 'R'
V C	Last phoneme previous block : vowel Phoneme that follows : consonant.	'fi' 'nally'	'F', 'AY' 'N', 'AH', 'L', 'TY'
C V	Last phoneme previous block : consonant Phoneme that follows : vowel.	'stars' 'up'	'S', 'T', 'AA', 'R', 'Z' 'AH', 'P'
C C	Last phoneme previous block : consonant Phoneme that follows : consonant.	'as' 'they'	'AE', 'Z' 'DH', 'EY'

Table 2: Every valid transition in 4 categories

try to see if this information can help us understand when performers line up lyrics with the beat.

An example presented in fig 24, 'glimmer' is divided into 'gli' and 'mmer' :

- The performer should make the transition between 'gli' and 'mmer' at 4.226s
- However, the phoneme timings extracted by the model presented in [46] informs us that 'M' starts at 4.096s and 'ER' starts at 4.16s
- Therefore, we can consider that the performer is early for this transition (130 ms of delay)
- We can also note that 'IH' is a vowel and 'M' is also a consonant, therefore this vowel-consonant transition (also noted V|C) is happening earlier than what it should be.

Analysis

From the annotations prepared for the AV_PhonemeBeatSync dataset, we are going to compute :

- An histogram of lateness for all the transitions and all performers, regardless of the phonetic involved.
- Compute the histograms of the delay for various phonetic transitions. First for all the performers, and then for the performers grouped by experience, to see if there seems to be a difference between the categories, or if we can generalize the data.

We are going to divide every valid transition in 4 categories : cf Table 2

To know if a phoneme is a vowel or a consonant, we follow the indication of the

CMU Dictionary ¹ that says that they based themselves on the ARPAbet symbol set ². Even though the analysis is just an example of what could be done, we hope that our analysis will show interesting results, and raise some questions. Here is some predictions that we can make :

- The delay histogram for all the performances regardless of the phonetic transition could be approximated by a normal distribution. We can believe that this normal distribution would be centered around a 0ms, with some standard deviation.
- We should observe a difference in the delays for various types of phonetic transitions. When singing, natural emphasis is made on the vowels, while the consonants are sometimes sacrificed.
- We could think that performers with more experience would be more accurate on the timings than beginners.

4.1.3 Where do people line up phonemes with the beat

We've seen before the analysis strategy to understand when people are lining up lyrics with the beat.

Because we have the ground truth of the rhythm, we know what lyrics they are supposed to sing and when they actually utter the phonemes, we can actually check what is uttered when the person feels the beat.

An example presented above Fig 24, we know that :

- The transition is supposed to happen at 4.22 seconds
- The 'M' phoneme started being uttered at 4.096 seconds
- The 'ER' phoneme started being uttered at 4.16 seconds.

We can therefore deduce that, when the performer felt the beat, the phoneme he was uttering was 'ER', with a margin of 60ms. The performer singing this extract therefore put the emphasis on the vowel, consciously or not.

Here, we have a scenario where we have a C1V1|C2V2 transition, and the beat is felt on V2, the second vowel.

The analysis : We are going to repeat this analysis for a selected set of transitions

¹<http://www.speech.cs.cmu.edu/cgi-bin/cmudict>

²<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ARPABET>

(presented below) on the whole AV_PhonemeBeatSync dataset. By averaging over the whole dataset, we should have some insight on where the performers are aligning their pronunciation with the beat.

We are also doing the same analysis with some latency applied to the detected onsets: 100ms earlier, 50ms earlier, 25ms earlier, 25ms later and 50ms later.

Our set of transitions is the following :

- xC1V1|V2C2x - ex : the middle of ‘heavens’ (HH EH | V AH N Z)
- xV1|C2V2x - ex : the middle of ‘coming’ (K AH | M IH NG)
- xV1C1|C2V2x - ex : from ‘in’ to ‘the’ (IH N | DH AH)
- xC1|V2C2x - ex : from ‘shapes’ to ‘and’ (SH EY P S | AE N D)
- xV1C1|V2x - ex : from ‘such’ to ‘a’ (S AH CH | AH)

We are not taking into account the potential phonemes before and after the transition, therefore there might be some leaks : for a xC1|V2C2x transition, the emphasis might be on a “hidden” V1.

Even if the analysis is partial and could be made for a larger set of transitions, we hope to find some interesting and consistent results across the transition sets.

We could predict that the emphasis would be put on the vowels. As seen in the state of the art, when singing, the vowels are sustained and the intelligibility is reduced i.e. the pronunciation of consonants is less important.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Classification of a performer

Results from LazyPredict

We present the bests results obtained with LazyPredict in the tables 3 and 4. All the results are in the Appendix.

Figure 27: Confusion matrix of the ExtraTreeClassifier - unbalanced dataset

Figure 28: Confusion matrix of the BernoulliNB - balanced dataset

Model - Classifier	Accuracy	Bal. Acc.	F1 Sc.
ExtraTree	0.447	0.29	0.472
Bagging	0.511	0.285	0.514
AdaBoost	0.372	0.281	0.402
RandomForest	0.617	0.261	0.526
KNeighbors	0.457	0.26	0.467

Table 3: Lazy Predict results for the unbalanced dataset - 5 bests models

Model	Acc.	Bal. Acc.	F1 Sc.
BernoulliNB	0.483	0.494	0.484
AdaBoostClass.	0.448	0.481	0.441
BaggingClass.	0.345	0.350	0.321
KNeighborsClass.	0.345	0.350	0.297
CalibratedClass.	0.310	0.337	0.293

Table 4: Lazy Predict results for the balanced dataset - 5 bests models

For the unbalanced dataset, we can see that the best classifier found without the default parameters is ExtraTreeClassifier. The raw accuracy is 0.45, meaning that we are close to the full randomness.

However, the balanced dataset gives us an accuracy of 0.49. A dummy classifier (a classifier that makes predictions that ignore the input feature) would have an accuracy of 0.25.

We plot the confusion matrix of the model giving us the best result on the dataset.

Simple Neural Network

Figure 29: Accuracy & Loss for the unbalanced dataset

Figure 30: Accuracy & Loss for the balanced dataset

Our simple architecture gives us these results (Fig. 29 & Fig. 30). For the unbalanced dataset, we can see that the overfitting starts appearing around the epoch n°100. At this time, the validation accuracy is nearly 0.55. The dataset being unbalanced with nearly 54% of the dominant class, our neural network doesn't give us any interesting results. For the balanced dataset however, the overfitting starts appearing around the epoch n°120. At this time, the validation accuracy is nearly 0.44. Even though the accuracy is not very high, this result is encouraging.

4.2.2 When do performers line up lyrics with the beats

The latency histogram for all the transitions for each performer is presented Fig.31. In order to approximate our various distributions with a curve and represent it as close to reality as it could be, we are going to use a Gaussian Kernel-Density Esti-

Figure 31: Distribution of latency for every transitions

Figure 32: Latency for various phonetic transitions

mation (Gaussian KDE³. It is a way to estimate the Probability Density Function (PDF) of a random variable in a non-parametric way.

Fig.31 therefore shows the histogram of delay and also the approximation made using Gaussian KDE. We can see that, on average, the transitions are 130ms early, with most of them happening between 191ms early and 62ms early.

We now show in Fig.32 the approximated distributions of latency for the different phonetic transitions, with all the performers.

We can see that the means are very different for each type of phonetic transition. Transiting to a vowel, seems to cause a lower latency than transiting to a consonant. Fig.33 is a boxplot of the various latencies for the 2-level phonetic transitions. The analysis is made independently for the different levels of the performers.

We see that the difference between the Beginners, the Casuals and the Experienced is quite neglectable, while the Professionals seem to be more accurate.

We can also see that transiting to a vowel is always more accurate than having to transit to a consonant, and this regardless of the experience singing.

³https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/reference/generated/scipy.stats.gaussian_kde.html

Figure 33: Latency for various phonetic transitions for the different categories of performers

4.2.3 Where do people line up phonemes with the beat

The Fig.34 shows the results of our analysis. We can see that the emphasis is consistently put on the coming vowel (nearly 70% of the time), no matter the position. We then show in Fig. 35 the results for several values of latency.

4.3 Discussion

The various analyses that we conducted here are simple ones, that are preliminary to more detailed ones. It is important to note that those results might be slightly biased by the errors resulting from the phoneme timing extraction.

4.3.1 Classification of a performer based on the latency :

For this task, we used 2 datasets : the unbalanced, full version of AV_PhonemeBeatSync and a balanced subset of AV_PhonemeBeatSync.

For the unbalanced version, we find without surprise that the results are non conclusive, and close to complete randomness.

Figure 34: Proportions of phoneme uttered when the beat happens, for various phonemic transitions

For the balanced version, however, we have interesting results. The BernoulliNB classifier gave us 48% accuracy while complete randomness would have given 25% accuracy. The simple neural network performs less well, with a 44% accuracy.

It is far from some previous results (correlation with Pearson factor of 82% obtained by Tsai et Al. in [27]), but the histogram resulting from this simplistic approach could inform a machine learning model like in [33].

Even if our task leaves out very little room for creativity, personal interpretation or mistakes, it still seems that there are some differences between the various types of singers. However, our dataset is very small, and would require more data to show more consistent and trustworthy results.

4.3.2 When do performers line up lyrics with the beat :

We've computed the latency for a set of phonetic transitions, and for various performers. As seen in Fig.31, the mean transition is 130ms early, and it seems that very few of them are 'on time' or early. This seems very surprising as we initially thought that people would randomly be early or late on the beat, a sum of random individual elements giving us a normal distribution centered around 0. However, it seems that this is not what happened. The histogram could not be approximated

Figure 35: Proportions of phoneme uttered when the beat happens, for various phonemic transitions and for various latency values

by the normal law, and it seems that it is skewed to the left (mean is inferior to the median).

We gave a precise text to the singers and asked them to sing some words at some precise timing. It seems that, for our experiment, performers were very early. We compared the ground truth of the beat they were hearing and the timing where the first phoneme that they had to sing was uttered. And almost every time, the performers were early on this task.

We can conclude here, and say that every singer thought the text differently, and put the emphasis on another phoneme, somewhere in the text to sing.

We can however see potential explanations that would mitigate this conclusion :

- Histogram are made with the information of all the singers regardless of their skills, with a strong bias for Casual singers.
- The fact that the performers have to read the upcoming lyrics while performing, pushing them to think ahead.
- They have a metronomic tick in their ear while performing. Anticipation and fear of being out-of-time could explain this latency.
- The errors when extracting the timings of the phonemes is not meaningful enough to explain the skewness and latency.

In Fig. 32, we plotted the approximated distributions of latency for different phonetic transitions, with for all the performers mixed. We can say that the differences are meaningful. Between the mean latency for a V|C transition and a C|V transition, there is nearly 140ms. Whenever the next phoneme to utter after the perceived beat is a vowel, the latency is very low. On the other hand, uttering a consonant will mean a high latency. This is probably because after the consonant, there is a high chance of having a vowel that could be where the performer unconsciously puts the emphasis.

Some possible explanations however :

- The 2-level transitions that we study don't account for the phonemes before or after, and we can believe that those phonemes can matter (coarticulation process).

- The dataset contains some vowels sustained that end in the next block, the consonant being sung early could therefore be a way of having some time to breath. Example : ‘light’ is divided in 2 blocks : ‘L’, ‘AY’ | ‘T’.

Finally, the boxplot presented in Fig. 33 shows us that there is not that much difference between the Beginners, the Casuals and the Experimented. The means and the quartiles of every type of transition is somewhat similar. However, when compared to the professionals, they seem to be more consistent. Narrower boxplot, and the mean latency is slightly lower than the others.

As an overall conclusion on this analysis, we can say that regardless of the experience, the performers were always early. However, having to sing a vowel will reduce the latency. Most likely because the performers are putting the emphasis on the vowels, when having to sing a text. It makes sense with what has been observed : when singing, natural emphasis is made on the vowels. They are more sustained and are carrying the emotion, whereas the intelligibility is reduced and therefore the consonants sometimes become accessories.

4.3.3 Where do people line up phonemes with the beat

This analysis is going to complement the previous analysis. We previously saw that the performers tend to not line up the text as requested, but they are rather interpreting the lyrics, and they seem to line up the lyrical content by themselves. We are now going to verify what type of phoneme (consonant or vowel) is uttered by a performer when the beat happens. Fig. 34 shows us that the emphasis is indeed put on the vowel. Nearly 70% of the time, the coming vowel is being uttered when the beat occurs.

However, when we inspect the data closely, we notice that sometimes the difference between a new phoneme and the beat location is very close. We therefore do the same analysis, but we add some latency (positive or negative) on the beat ground truth.

We’ve seen previously that the transiting to a consonant led to more latency. We have here two examples to analyze deeper with the help of Fig. 35 :

- For a V|C transition (here xV1|C2V2x), we can see that 100ms before the

actual onset, 72% of the time, the performers already transited to C2. At 50ms before the actual onset, the new text is already being uttered, and 25% of the time the performers have finished uttering the consonant and are already in the process of uttering the vowel. At the onset, 68% is uttering the vowel.

- For a C|C transition (here xV1C1|C2V2x), we can see that 100ms before the actual onset, 57% of the time, the performers have already transited to C2, and are preparing the V2. 25ms before the actual onset, 94% of the time the performers are uttering the new text, and 40% are already in the vowel and have finished the consonant. When the onset happens, 65% are on the vowel.

When transiting to a vowel, the performers are more accurate. For a V|V transition (xC1V1|V2C2x), most of the transition happens between 50ms and 25ms earlier.

However, when transiting to a vowel, the performers are more likely to be on time. The transition starts later, and seems to be smoother (no abrupt change of percentage within a 25 ms range).

The next text to sing being CV or VC doesn't change the fact that, 50ms after the beat the vowel is still being uttered on 90% of the occurrences, no matter the transition. This shows that the vowel is indeed sustained in time, while the consonant is short and transitory.

The results correspond to what we were expecting : the performers are putting emphasis on the vowel, and the consonant is just a preparation that will lead to a vowel.

To the question “where do people feel the beat”, we can say that, for our experiment, they feel the beat and put the emphasis on the vowel.

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Discussing the results

5.1.1 AV_PhonemeBeatSync

We have gathered a brand new audiovisual dataset, one of the first available at the moment, and the only one with non-anonymous video content available (upon request). We also differentiate ourselves with several elements :

- Having the ground truth or the rhythmic pattern perceived by the performer while he sings
- 60FPS - 720p video for high quality and precise facial information.
- Facial landmarks already extracted and openly accessible.
- Providing annotations to facilitate the future use of this dataset.

There are, however, some elements that needs to be mentioned :

- The performances in itself are somewhat biased. Performers were hearing a metronomic pattern while singing, forcing them into respecting the rhythm. This is what we wanted to study: how would they line the phonemes in a syllable. However, it comes with a performance that is, sometimes, not exactly natural.
- The content is heavily biased toward the western culture.

- People were asked to classify themselves in categories which introduces a human bias. There are also more casual singers than others. This dataset was also created in the context of SkyNote ¹, a music learning application. The bias in casual performers makes sense in this context, as those people will be the main target of the product.
- There is a bias in the performers' diversity. While the male/female ratio is almost balanced (54/46%), almost all of the performers are white, and there is little ethnic diversity. For an AudioVisual dataset, this could be a major issue. This can, however, be mitigated by gray-scaling the videos, or working with the face landmarks.
- Some performances are more 'rhythmic reading' than singing. This can be explained by the fatigue of the performers, their potential lack of experience or them not feeling comfortable with the content.

During the recordings, we encountered some issues that appear in the final dataset:

- Some audio recordings have an electric hum that was unnoticed during the recording. The choice has been made to not touch those recordings, and to let the users do some filtering if needed.
- To enhance facial visibility in video recording, a directed light illuminated the face. Yet, discomfort arose among some performers, and glasses-wearers experienced light reflections, occasionally reducing face prominence in recordings.
- Performers were standing up during the recordings, and the camera is never at the same position. This default can be mitigated by the fact that it brings some diversity in the data. Moreover, because they had to read the lyrics, they almost all had their faces slightly facing the left.

Regarding the annotation process, some elements:

- The text-related annotations, there could be some issues as the annotation presents the ground truth, but not how the person interpreted the ground truth.
- The most problematic element is the data related to the timings of the phonemes. This process was fully automatic, and manual verification would take a huge amount of time. As seen in the results, we found a very good accuracy for an

¹<https://appskynote.com/landing>

immense majority of timings, but there are still some remaining issues that could slightly influence the analysis.

- Regarding the facial landmarks extraction, some points of the face are not sometimes not very stable. This can be mitigated by filtering the data, or smoothing it out over several frames.

5.1.2 Analysis

Following a preliminary analysis, we've stumbled upon some rather intriguing outcomes. It turns out that, when it comes to singing, performers not only put their emphasis on vowels by sustaining them, but also concentrate their attention on these specific points. They seem to perceive the rhythmic beat as a cue for precisely when to enunciate these vowels.

There's a distinct connection between people and the beat residing within the vowels. Nonetheless, a more profound analysis is necessary to unearth the exact placement of this beat within a vocal signal. It's conceivable that comprehending the role of phonemes and the coarticulation process holds the key to unraveling effective beat detection in singing tasks. Furthermore, mastering these aspects could potentially push the boundaries of realistic vocal synthesis.

5.2 Future work

The analysis gave us an insight on where do people line up phonemes in a syllable with the beat, but we did not go into the details. We stayed with a simplistic model of putting every vowel together and every consonant together, and did not distinguish the other phonemes that are at stake in the coarticulation process. We can identify various categories :

- 'stops' consonants ('P', 'B', 'M', 'T' ...) : Produced by completely stopping the airflow in the oral cavity for a fraction of time.
- 'fricatives' consonants ('F', 'V', 'TH' ...) : Produced by obstructing the airflow to cause friction.

- ‘glides’ consonants (‘Y’, ‘W’) : Produced by a very little obstruction of the airflow, always followed by a vowel.
- ‘High’, ‘Mid’ or ‘Low’ vowels : Position of the tongue in the mouth.
- ‘Front’, ‘Central’ or ‘Back’ vowels : Position of the tongue in the mouth.

AV_PhonemeBeatSync was created to help researchers by giving them some data to work with. The dataset could be used for :

- Automatic Lyric Transcription tasks for singing. It’s an ongoing area of research, and there is no doubt that our dataset could be used extensively for this task.
- Beat detection for a singing task. As mentioned in [2], “there is no existing dataset containing clean vocal audio with beat/downbeat annotations”. Here, we are offering some valuable data that can be used.
- Audiovisual singing synthesis. As mentioned in [5], a complete singing face is rich in emotions, and predicting the small facial expressions that occur when someone sings could improve the existing results.
- Understanding the coarticulation mechanism that happens when someone sings. Because of the low granularity of our visual data, we are hoping that a machine learning model could understand this phenomenon and give interesting results when estimating the timing for a single transition.
- A Singing Skill Evaluation task. As said in [31], a lack in the datasets related to singing are the annotations related to the quality of singing. While the recordings in AV_PhonemeBeatSync are not precisely criticized by experts, we have some vague idea of the experience of the performers. This dataset being heavily biased toward casual singers could inform some analysis related to less experienced performers.
- Another Singing Skill Evaluation task. Because the performers were asked to put the emphasis on the rhythm, and that the pitch was completely free, an interesting rhythmic singing evaluation task could be completed. For example, using the approach made in [33] or in [34], but informing the analysis with a latency histogram on top of a pitch histogram.
- A classification task of a singer’s performance based on their rhythmic information, following the approach proposed by [30], but adapting it to our

context.

- Any project that we can think of involving audio and video.

Even if our dataset is rather small ($\tilde{7}$ h of content), it is possible to use various data augmentation techniques to increase the diversity and the volume of content, therefore making a machine learning model more robust. Examples of methods are mentioned in 3.3.2

Figure 36: Example of a possible machine learning architecture that could use AV_PhonemeBeatSync

Figure 37: Example of input data for our proposed architecture

We propose an architecture in Fig.36 for a deep learning model that could answer our question of predicting the latency given the phonetic transition. The methodology for preparing the input data is explained with an example showing the transition between the syllables ‘mmer’ and ‘gli’ in Fig. 37 :

- The green bars represent the beat location ground truth (felt by the performer). They are separated by 0.6s.
- The red bar represents where the beginning of the ‘G’ phoneme, the first phoneme of the new text was detected.

- The time difference between the green bar and the red bar is x , it corresponds to the latency that we want to estimate. We could also estimate the latency for the ‘L’ phoneme, and the ‘IH’ phoneme.
- The small extract would consist of 0.6s of audio and the corresponding video frames (36). Those 0.6s seconds would be randomly located between 2 green bars as long as the red bar is contained within those 0.6 seconds.

With this method and some data augmentation techniques, there should be enough content to train a deep learning algorithm and obtain an interesting approximation of latency for various phonetic transitions.

A small description of the architecture :

- An as input : small audio/video extracts and the associated timings and phonemes.
- The audio would go to an Audio Encoder consisting of a Bi-RNN with LSTMs. As mentioned in [53], coarticulation is influenced by the past, but also by the future. Having 2 layers simultaneously in both directions would inform the model.
- The video (whether actual video or just the facial landmarks) would go to a video encoder, consisting of CNN layers to extract the embeddings from the facial informations, and then a Bi-RNN with LSTMs, that would introduce the temporal aspects of the analysis.
- The result of those encoders could go to a feature fusion block, and then be mixed with the phonetic information.
- All this would go to a dense layer before going to the output layer who would give us the predicted time difference between the beat groundtruth and the beat detected.

5.3 Conclusion

The central objective of this project was to delve into the domain of multimodal singing analysis, and to identify existing gaps and potential areas for advancement. After some exploration, it appeared that there was a lack of qualitative multimodal

data in this field. There was no audiovisual singing dataset, no dataset including beat ground truth and clear rhythmic information. Moreover, no work found for singing skill evaluation was integrating the coarticulation elements. To the best of our knowledge, no research discusses trying to find where a singer feels the beat, and how a singer lines up phonemes with the beat for some syllables.

Our work addresses these gaps. AV_PhonemeBeatSync was designed to propell the research in audiovisual singing, and more than 7 hours of content was gathered. We believe that this dataset could be used in several analysis and synthesis tasks and we hope that it will be useful.

Parallel to this, a secondary goal was to analyze the data collected, and try to answer the questions that motivated our research with a simple analysis. Even if it was not possible to classify a performer's experience based on his rhythmic latency with a high accuracy, we still managed to obtain 48% accuracy, two times more than a completely random classification. We believe that our experiment constrained the scope for artistic expression and individual interpretation, and it would be difficult to differentiate the performers' experience just based on rhythm here. However, we believe that using latency histograms to inform a machine learning model could lead to good results.

We found that, for a variety of phonetic transitions, the performers were most of the time early on the beat. Although instructed to vocalize specific text at precise timings, they often diverged from these instructions, placing emphasis on vowels. The consonants seem to be lined up around the vowels to enhance intelligibility and lyrical clarity. This behavior seems to be consistent across the performer's experience, even if experienced and professionals are more accurate. We concede that the controlled nature of our experiment might limit its applicability to real-world scenarios.

The analysis we did showed that the AV_PhonemeBeatSync database contains valuable data that is worth mining, and could be use to train and evaluate neural networks.

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Appendix A

Lyrics ChatGPT

Table 5: Lyrics lined up - From 1.1 (top left) to 3.2 (bottom right)

Gli	mmer	Gli	mmer	li	ttle	li-	-ght
Shi	ning	through	the	dark	of	ni-	-ght
Spar	kling	stars	up	in	the	sky-	
Gui	ding	ships	as	they	pass	by-	
Twin	kle	Sprin-	kle	shi	ning	bri-	-ght
In	the	heavens	day	and	ni-	-ght	
Whi	sper	shish-	sper	li	ttle	bree-	-ze
Mo	ving	soft	ly	through	the	tree-	-s
Fee	ling	leaves	with	gen	tle	tou-	-ch
Brin	ging	calm	we	need	so	mu-	-ch
Mur	mur	mur	mur	in	the	ai-	-r
Whisp	ring	se	crets	eve	ry	whe-	-re
Rum	ble	fum	ble	thun	der	sou-	-nd
E	choes	ro	lling	all	a	rou-	-nd
Fla	shing	bolts	of	light	ning	bri-	-ght
fi-	lling	dark	ness	with	their	li-	-ght
thun	der	blun-	der	ro	lling	u-	-p
Til	the	storm	is	fi	nally	go-	-ne
Ri	pple	sti	pple	in	the	strea-	-m
Gli	tter	in	the	sun's	bright	bea-	-m
Flo	wing	gent	ly	down	the	way	
Re	flect	beau	ty	night	and	day	
Glis	ten	glis	ten	crys	tal	clea-	-r
In	the	wa	ter	al	ways	he-	-re
Chir	ping	Chir	ping	li	ttle	bir-	-d
Sing	ing	sweet	ly	can	be	hea-	-rd
Me	lo	dies	that	fill	the	ai-	-r
Brin	ging	joy	be	yond	com	pa-	-re
Sin	ging	la	zy	in	the	tree-	-s
Fi	lling	hearts	with	har	mo	ni-	-es
Hu	mming	hu	mming	buzz	ing	bee-	-ee
Fly	ing	swift	ly	wild	and	free-	-ee
Dan	cing	a	round	bright	sun	flow-	-ers
Earn	ing	po	llen	ev-	ry	hou-	-r
Buzz	y	ruzz	y	all	a	rou-	-nd
In	the	gar	den	buzz	ing	sou-	-nd
Old	brew	mas	ter	brewed	some	bee-	-rs
pale	ale	stout	and	nut	brown	ale	And
in	his	farm	he	loves	to	si-	-ing
as	he	brews	his	li	quid	things	With a
puff	chug	here	and a	pour	tour	there	
here's a	sip	here's a	swig	every	where	chuga	lug
Old	brew	mas	ter	brewed	some	bee-	-rs
im	pe	rial	por	ter	!!		
Bi	lly	brought	some	beers	to	sha-	-re
cold	and	fun	ky	smel-	ling		And
in	his	cool	ler	he	does	chill	
he	feels	su	per	hea	ted		With a
kink	wink	here	and a	wouf	douf	there	
here's a	burp	there's a	cheer	every	one	toa-	-sting
Bi	lly	brought	some	beers	to	sha-	-re
a	sweet	ba	rrel	age-	-ed		
Je	nny	brewed	some	beer	at	ho-	-me
Am	ber	bar	ley	tann-	-ic	wine	But
in	her	place	she	loves	to	try	out
plen	ty of	dif-	-ferent	fla	vours		With a
stir	wind	here	and a	pour	jour	there	
here's a	sniff	there's a	taste	every	glass	bone	dry
Je	nny	brewed	some	beer	at	ho-	-me
no	one	left	up	stand	ing		
Mike	and	Sue	went	to	a	ba-	-r
to	en	joy	dark	la	gers		And
in	the	pub	they	loved	to	ta-	-ste
all	kind	of	fer	men	ted	juice.	With a
sash	bosh	here	and a	pow	how	there	
here's a	joke	here's a	laugh	give	me a	nother	glass
Mike	and	Sue	went	to	a	ba-	-r
For	some	joy	ful	ti-	-me		
Win	ter's	here	old	su	mmer's	gone	now
Cold	wind	blow	ing	snow	flakes	nea-	-r
i	cy	roads	with	fros	ty	tree-	-ees
Wrap	up	warm	or	you	will	free-	-ze
Chi	lly	ni-	-ight	trou	bled	mi-	-ind
Fi	re	roa-	-oar	through	the	da-	-rk
co	zy	blan	kets	fan	cy	spa	ces
Win	ter	pow-	-er	fo	re	ver	
Sli	per-	-y	ice	please	be	care	ful
Stay	in	si	de	take	my	advi	ce
hot	cho	co	late	warm	marsh	me	lows
Win	ters	treat	can	not	be	bea-	-t
Ski	ing	is	fun	fa	lling	is	not
Race	down	hill	sides	win	ter's	run	
Friends	fa	mi	ly	all	to	ge	ther
joy	ful	laugh	ter	life	is	goo-	-d
Snow	ball	throw	ing	snow	man	buil	ding
duck	jump	dodge	fall	hold	on	ti-	-ght
Fros	ty	no	ses	free	zing	bo	ttoms
win	ter	fun	that	we	all	cra-	-ve
A	big	snow	fall	fro	zen	bu	llets
Spar	kling	bright	as	win	ter's	fa-	-ng
Crys	tal	beau	ty	fro	zen	de	light
Na	ture	art	is	in	plain	si-	-ght
Ski	ing	slo-	-opes	snow	board	tri-	-icks
down	hill	rush	ing	fun	ky	ri	ders
Fresh	snow	pow	der	ski	boots	tigh	ter
Win	ter	spor-	-ts	pu-	-re	de	light
Sea	son's	fini	shed	win	ter's	end	ing
Spring	al	most	here	my	good	old	friend
Good	bye	win	ter	un	til	next	year
Thank	you	dear	ly	nice	memo-	-ri-	-es

Table 6: Lyrics lined up - From 4.1 (top left) to 6.2 (bottom right)

In	the	mor	ning	when	we	wake	up
Birds	are	chir	ping	it's	day	brea-	-k
Co	ffee	bre	wing	smells	so	goo-	-ood
Start	the	day	just	like	we	shou-	-ld
Rise	and	shine	with a	brand	new	out	look
New	dis	trac	tions	for	a	whi-	-le
Lu	cky	chan	ces	will	a	rrive	And
let	us	seize	them	and	a	stou-	-nd
In	the	work	place	bu	sy	peo	ple
Mee	tings	e	mails	dead	line	plea-	-se
Co	la	bo-	-ra	ting	with	a	team
A	chie	ving	goals	for	our	drea-	-m
Su	cces	is	near	we	can	fee-	-eel
Hard	work	pays	off	it's	the	dea-	-l
Per	se	ve	rance	is	the	se	cret
To	un	lock	our	ob	jec	tives	
In	the	e	vening	as	we	wind	down
Pea	ceful	mo	ments	can	be	fou-	-nd
Rea	ding	books	or	wa-	-tching	mo	vies
Re	la	xing	be	fore	we	do-	-ze
Fa	mi	ly	time	is	moti	va	tion
Love	and	laugh	ter be	yond	mea	su-	-re
Gra	t'ful	for	the	ones	we	hold	dear
Che	ri	shing	as	we	grow	old	
In	this	world	so	much	to	wit	ness
End	less	won	ders	wild	and	free	
Trav	v'ling	to	whole	new	lo	ca	tions
Ex	pe	rien	cing	diff-	-rent	thi-	-ngs
Lear	ning	from	the	o	ther	cul	tures
Ex	pan	ding	ho-	-ri	zons	fur	ther
U	ni	ty	a	mong	all	na	tions
Har	mo	ny	with	ce	le	bra	tions
In	the	fif	ties	rock	was	bo-	-rn
Re	be	llion	a	gainst	the	no-	-rms
El	vis	Pres	ley	sha	king	hi-	-ps
Gui	tars	wai	ling	ca-	-tchy	ri-	-ffs
Rock	and	roll	a	cul	tural	bla-	-st
Trans	for	ming	mu	sic	al	pa-	-st
Bea	ties	a	rrived	from	Mer	sey	
To	shift	mu	sic's	des	ti	ny	
John	Paul	George	and	Rin	go	play-	-ed
Me	lo	di-	-es	for	ever	sway-	-ed
Ser	gent	Pe	ppers	mas	ter	pie-	-ce
Rock's	e	vo	lu	tion	in	crea-	-sed
Wood	stock	peace	love	in	the	ai-	-r
Hi	ppies	groo	ving	with	no	sca-	-re
Ji	mi	Hen	Drix	gui	tar	go-	-d
His	so	los	were	heard	a	broa-	-d
Ja	nis	Jop	lin	soul	ful	voi-	-ce
Come	lis	ten	we	will	re	joi-	-ce
Se	ven	ties	brought	a	heavy	sou-	-nd
The	im	pact	shall	be	pro	fou-	-nd
Spee	dy	gui	tars	hea	vy	me	tal
Drums	as	loud	as	some	ke	ttle	bell
Do	not	for	get	the	giam	ro-	-ck
Queen	Bo-	-wie	loved	the	ba-	-ro-	-que
Punk	a	ppeared	raw	e	ner	gy	
Ra	mones	Pis	tois	a	nar	chy	
Grunge	mu	si	cian's	wild	spi	ri-	-t
Nir	va	na's	fan	fa	vo	ri-	-te
Al	ter	na	tive	rock	em	bra-	-ce
Sha	pping	the	mu	sic	land	sca-	-pe
Rock	per	sists	e	volves	with	ti-	-me
Gen	res	blen	ding	boun	d'ries	pri-	-me
From	sta	dium	to	in	die	char-	-ts
Rock	mu	sic's	le	ga	cy	stan-	-ds
Throug	h	highs	and	lows	spi	rit	stay
h							-s
Twin	kle	Twin	kle	time	less	ta-	-les
Bar	ce	lo	na	ci	ty	gran-	-d
Beach	moun	tai-	-n	sea	and	san-	-d
Go	thic's	quar	ter	co	bbled	lane	Ram
bla	with	out	a	rai-	-n		
Of	mu	sic	laugh	ter	de	li-	-ght
Ca	ta	la-	-n	shi	ning	bri-	-ight
With	cul	ture	art	his	to-	-ry	it's
all	I	want	to	see-	-ee		
Food	in	bar	celo	na	is	ni-	-ce
Good	ta	pa-	-s	it's	all	fi-	-ne
Sa	vor	sea	food	from	the	sea	or
chu	rros	in	the	stree-	-t		
Wine	flows	free	ly	all	night	lo-	-ng
Co	ming	fro-	-m	Mont	ser	rat	
Of	pa	ssion	fla	vour	ro	mance	You
have	me	in	a	tra-	-nce		
Mo	nu	ments	are	quite	a	si-	-ght
Sa	gra	da		Fa	mi	li-	-a
Gau	di's	hou	ses	cra	zy	shapes	And
all	the	fun	ky	li-	-ghts		
We	have	such	a	beauti	ful	par-	-k
Beau	ty	he-	-re	knows	no	bou-	-nds
With	mo	dern	and	ol	der	art	This
ci	ty	ne	ver	stops	to	slee-	-p
Spi	rit	of	the	ci	ty	roa-	-m
Foot	ball	clu-	-b	world	re	know-	-n
We	dance	sing	and	ce	le	brate	While
it	is	not	too	la-	-te		
From	the	moun	tain	sa	cred	pea-	-k
to	the	bea-	-ch	where	sea	mee-	-ts
This	place	is	a	dream	come	true	Bar
celo	na	I	love	you-	-ou		

Appendix B

Mediapipe & Dlib

We present below in Table 7 examples of the landmarks extracted for one frame :

- First row is the landmark extracted using Dlib and reconstructed on a black background and on the performers face
- Second row is the landmark extracted using Mediapipe and reconstructed on a black background and on the performers face
- Third row is the landmark extracted using Dlib & Mediapipe and reconstructed on a black background and on the performers face

Table 7: Comparison of extractions between Dlib & Mediapipe

Appendix C

LazyPredict results

Model	Accuracy	Balanced Accuracy	F1 Score
ExtraTreeClassifier	0.447	0.29	0.472
BaggingClassifier	0.511	0.285	0.514
AdaBoostClassifier	0.372	0.281	0.402
RandomForestClassifier	0.617	0.261	0.526
KNeighborsClassifier	0.457	0.26	0.467
LGBMClassifier	0.532	0.255	0.522
RidgeClassifierCV	0.511	0.254	0.518
NearestCentroid	0.426	0.252	0.485
DummyClassifier	0.649	0.25	0.511
SVC	0.649	0.25	0.511
CalibratedClassifierCV	0.649	0.25	0.511
QuadraticDiscriminantAnalysis	0.649	0.25	0.511
ExtraTreesClassifier	0.617	0.249	0.522
LabelPropagation	0.170	0.247	0.111
LabelSpreading	0.170	0.247	0.111
RidgeClassifier	0.489	0.246	0.501
DecisionTreeClassifier	0.436	0.244	0.468
LogisticRegression	0.415	0.244	0.452
Perceptron	0.468	0.242	0.498
XGBClassifier	0.479	0.234	0.485
BernoulliNB	0.479	0.234	0.496
LinearDiscriminantAnalysis	0.415	0.233	0.459
PassiveAggressiveClassifier	0.372	0.224	0.406
SGDClassifier	0.426	0.222	0.458
LinearSVC	0.394	0.221	0.435
GaussianNB	0.106	0.215	0.111

Table 8: LazyPredict for the unbalanced dataset

Model	Accuracy	Balanced Accuracy	F1 Score
BernoulliNB	0.483	0.494	0.484
AdaBoostClassifier	0.448	0.481	0.441
BaggingClassifier	0.345	0.350	0.321
KNeighborsClassifier	0.345	0.350	0.297
CalibratedClassifierCV	0.310	0.337	0.293
LogisticRegression	0.310	0.337	0.314
RidgeClassifier	0.310	0.337	0.268
SGDClassifier	0.310	0.319	0.315
NearestCentroid	0.310	0.319	0.309
RandomForestClassifier	0.310	0.319	0.305
XGBClassifier	0.276	0.288	0.269
RidgeClassifierCV	0.276	0.288	0.282
Perceptron	0.276	0.288	0.275
LinearDiscriminantAnalysis	0.276	0.269	0.270
ExtraTreesClassifier	0.241	0.256	0.247
DummyClassifier	0.172	0.250	0.051
LabelPropagation	0.276	0.250	0.119
LabelSpreading	0.276	0.250	0.119
LGBMClassifier	0.241	0.238	0.257
GaussianNB	0.241	0.238	0.222
DecisionTreeClassifier	0.241	0.238	0.246
PassiveAggressiveClassifier	0.207	0.225	0.204
SVC	0.207	0.225	0.183
LinearSVC	0.207	0.225	0.204
NuSVC	0.207	0.206	0.209
ExtraTreeClassifier	0.207	0.206	0.198
QuadraticDiscriminantAnalysis	0.172	0.156	0.168

Table 9: LazyPredict results for the balanced dataset